

All-Inclusive World: An Appraisal of *Fratelli Tutti* on Fraternity and Social Friendship

Soroj Mullick SDB

Bandel Church, West Bengal

Abstract: The Encyclical *Fratelli Tutti*, is an urgent appeal to all the citizens and faith-believers of the world to course-direct on a different path, for the survival of the world. The author makes a re-reading of the document which is impregnated with its social reflection, calling for social action through a creative social friendship and fraternity. This paper highlights on the theme of socio-political love, with more emphasis on God and religion. Positively, the author agrees that as a *Social Encyclical*, it would do well towards social friendship and support a culture of encounter. In this process, dialogue and proper use of media, could contribute much towards an ecumenical and global renewal. With an inclusive approach to life and faith, the author affirms the inter-faith fraternity for the common good. In this context, the Church in Asia has to fulfill its salvific mission in and through Christ, and that religious leaders will have to be authentic mediators in the name of human fraternity, by being at the service of all brothers and sisters.

Keywords: *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis, Social Friendship, Use of Media

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Introduction

The new encyclical *Fratelli Tutti* (FT) promotes Divine Oneness in every event and person, irrespective of race and creed, through social friendship, fraternal solidarity and dialogue while embracing all diversities. It promotes inclusivity in reference to the Biblical and Christian perspective of universal love for all. It is a call to disrupt our lives and pay attention to an encounter with reality, with a “challenge to our ecological, political, economic and social life” (Rowlands, 2020) through, “human fraternity and the care of creation” - the only paths forward for humanity (Francis, 2020). In the present case and context, holding on to the above premise, the encyclical is deemed a “radical blueprint for a post-coronavirus world” (Watkins, 2020).

*Intending to cater to the socio-spiritual and intellectual needs of the clergy and religious, here is a critical reflection on the need to commit oneself to God and to fellow-human beings, as inscribed in the FT. It takes a critical look into the world problems with a pastoral approach, through the lens of the present Christian experience in the midst of the Pandemic Covid-19, highlighting on socio-political love, with more emphasis on God and religion. The author affirms that religious freedom and dialogue without Christ, is non-admissible in anyway, and that the *Social Encyclical* would do well towards social friendship and support a culture of encounter, for a fraternal society, in order to heal all wounds of alienation and bigotry. The paper also puts forth an Asian-Indian reading of FT while making certain critical observations.*

Universal World

FT begins with a critique of current events and the problems existing: global conflict, natural disasters, climate change, migrants and right-wing populism caused by false economy which is based on liberal individualism. Francis talks of the resurgence of conflicts, resentment, divisions among peoples, the resurgence of “unhealthy ‘populism’“ and nationalism, generational ruptures, inequality

between women and men, consumerist fever, verbal violence on social networks, indifference towards the weakest, etc. He says, “For Christians, this way of thinking and acting is unacceptable, since it sets certain political preferences above deep convictions of our faith” (FT 39). Besides, often enough, the Church leaders in every age faced the temptation to do their own work, instead of God’s. This is a challenge on “how to be good workers in the Lord’s vineyard,” (Phil 4:6-9). Calling for a world without borders, he says, “Fraternity necessarily calls for something greater, which in turn enhances freedom and equality” (FT103). With this above background and focus, we proceed to highlight the importance of FT with its purpose and principle elements.

Beyond Boundaries

As the sense of transcendence decreases, the denial of human universalism sows the “seed of death for democracy”(Julliard, 2020). In such context, Francis provides a common framework. According to him, we become a “we” for the survival of our planet and our societies (Gaulmyn, 2020). The Good Samaritan (Lk 10:25-37), is about how we make others our neighbour and not about who is my neighbour. Paul Ricoeur said, “To be close to one’s neighbour is the very conduct of making oneself close” (Ricoeur, 1967, 113). We become universal without crushing individualities, or breaking up cultures. The pope writes, “The true worth of the different countries of our world is measured by their ability to think not simply as a country but also as part of the larger human family” (FT 141). FT, “echoes the vision of a world at the crossroads where the path we take will decide whether the inheritance that we leave to our grandchildren will be wasted or saved” (Hamilton, 2020). Therefore, the concept of *integral ecology* so evident in *Laudato Si’*, flows into FT on social friendship.

Political Love

Francis offers a “politics of love”, that is, forgiving, remembering and breaking the circle of violence through peace and justice. Religions have a role to play in promoting God’s ‘politics of love’. When God is removed from a society, “that society ends up adoring idols, and very soon men and women lose their way, their dignity is trampled and their rights violated” (Francis, 2014). Political love can be extended to our neighbours by ensuring that our politics and our social structures give every person exactly what they need to live a dignified life. FT, then, offers a challenge to the national political conscience, and also offers seeds of conversion, to upend their way of doing things. The words ‘politics’, ‘political’, and ‘politicians’ occur more than 100 times in the FT, precisely for a better kind of politics. Francis promotes a new socio-political model inspired by subsidiarity and solidarity based on “social love” and “political love”. Francis’ hopes that this vision becomes part of public systems of global governance, which has worsened, including the economy (during this COVID-19, the total wealth of billionaires has jumped to its highest level) (Faggioli, 2020).

God and Religion

Faith in God is in danger of dying today. As it is noted above, when God is removed from the public life, other fundamental rights and values are endangered. The open idea of “fraternity” risks for a reformer-Jesus, putting the Universal Church in a “dilemma” (Natoli, 2020). There is utmost need “of making God present in this world and giving men access to God” (Benedict XVI 2009). Such urgency is absent in FT. FT deals more on the dimension of “caritas,” and less of Transcendence (Natoli, 2020; Forte, 2020). In fact, Francis writes: “Let us return to promoting the good, for ourselves and for the whole human family, and thus advance together towards an authentic and integral growth” (FT 113). Christianity is turning into “Christus caritas” (FT 1-2, 286).

Authentic faith has to do with the whole of life and not just with our subjective convictions. The Religious leaders are slow to condemn unjust practices. Religions are to be “models of dialogue, brokers of peace, and bearers of the message of transcendent love” and religious leaders “are called to be true ‘people of dialogue’, a community of ‘a people’ to cooperate in building peace not as intermediaries but as authentic mediators” (FT 284; cf. FT 273). In order to build up God’s *Dharma Rajya*, leaders are to go through a Franciscan contemplative ‘political mysticism’, discerning the signs of the time (O’Connell, 8.10.2020). It is “only by identifying with the least” that we become brothers to all (FT 287; cf Sinasac, 2020). FT, therefore, is a call to collective conscience, and being an authentic and compassionate “wounded healer” (Nouwen, 1979).

One of the weak points of FT is, it bends “both the Church and religious freedom to a temporal dimension” (Scrosati, 2020). Francis writes on religious freedom as: “One fundamental human right [...] towards fraternity and peace” (FT 279). It evades the binding duty of the Church that “proclaims, and ever must proclaim Christ ‘the way, the truth, and the life’ (Jn 14:6). Instead, it adds: “The Church ‘has a public role over and above her charitable and educational activities.’ She works for ‘the advancement of humanity and of universal fraternity’”(FT 276). Gospel seems to be reduced to a temporal dimension, “of compassion, the tender love born of trust” (FT 277).

FT as an example of ‘thought leadership’(Rowlands 2020), perhaps is more accepted outside the Catholic world. It denounces all forms of culture that involve domination or social aggression, and invites a culture of encounter. What is needed is an open argument, involving careful analysis of the situation, real and existing evidence, formulation of hypothesis, drawn conclusions and action (Castellano, 2020).

Social Friendship, Encounter and Media

Social friendship in action, then, “is the set of practices that allow us to realise universal friendship as a way of life, as a habit” (Wells & Bordoni, 2020). FT confirm that it “makes true universal openness possible” with a “love capable of transcending borders” (FT 99). Social friendship is essential for a global culture of encounter, based on consensus and truth (cf. FT 198-214). It is a *new-normal* of acknowledging others, because “no one is useless and no one is expendable” (FT 215). But, in an era of relativism, social friendship can become ‘fake friendship’ and laws become “arbitrary impositions” (FT 206; cf. *Laudato Si*’ 123), and social media with “self-righteous posturing” (Barron, 2020), a mere “fake news”. Unless the “acknowledgement of the worth of every human person” (FT 106) is upheld, “there will be no future either for fraternity or for the survival of humanity” (FT 107).

Asian Face of FT

Within a ‘Roman’ political-cultural reality, Francis turns himself to be a pragmatist (Pertici, 2020) in regards to ecumenism and global reform, pursued by the ‘think-tank’ (opened with *Humanae Vitae*, 1968), around him. Francis emphasises on the polyhedral synodal structure of the Church, with “diversity reconciled”, while empowering the federation/conferences of local Churches. “If the Church is alive, it must always surprise” (Francis, 2014). The FABC report asserts that Asia has more than COVID-19 pandemic, and lacks peace and unity, that there needs to be ‘vaccines of compassion’ (Maung Bo, 2020), solidarity and justice after the model of the Good Samaritan (FT 67), and a ‘well-intentioned politics’ (O’Connell, 2020). FT invites all for reconciliation with God, humanity and the creation, with an open world and an open heart with a politics of love for the common good. The Church in Asia needs to condemn the greed and violence in Asia, and build collective consciousness, mobilise collective action and strive for the common good (FT 7), combatting discrimination (FT15). There

has to be a “primacy given to relationship, to the encounter with the sacred mystery of the other” (FT 277). As, “God has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity” (*Human Fraternity*, 2019) we explore together to lead a dignified, harmonious and peaceful life (Louis 2020, 57). We are to live “as a single human family” (FT 8).

Critical Observations

FT poses world’s problems - new forms of “civilized” inhumanity - to the very heart of the Christian faith: the transcendence of universal love that leads to universal fraternity (FT 56). FT as a “social encyclical” is the scale of conscience for the leaders. It

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makes an “economic” criticism of neo-liberal economy model, and its criminal consequences. Francis speaks of “digital campaigns of hatred and destruction” (FT 42). Francis offers a new modality of human coexistence with a universal vision for the world, but he mixes up populism and liberalism in a document on fraternity, expressing his political views (FT 156).

FT seems to revolve around social and humanitarian issues. It speaks of “sacrifices born of love”, for God is love (*subtitle*, FT 187-189); that all religions are equal; we are created in the image and likeness of God, therefore, we are brothers and sisters (FT 271); that we “*rethink our styles of life*” (FT 33), without “denying reality”. The Church, therefore, as a “*closely knit union with God and of the unity of the whole human race*”, it desires now to unfold more fully to the faithful of the Church and to the whole world its own inner nature and universal mission” (LG 1). Francis continues this task, through the path of social friendship and not so much of social justice (Pakaluk, 2020). There is little about salvation in Christ in FT. Besides,

FT carries strongly masculine connotations, and “does not accord women the same dignity and identical rights as men” (Paulin-Campbell, 2020).

Conclusion

As pastors, it is a time to “rethink how we live together on this cosmic speck of dust we call earth” (Cupich, 2020). As one single race, only through deep relationships as brothers and sisters do we “gradually come to know ourselves” (FT 69). The present pandemic has shown signs of hope, when the “Covid-Warriors” are like the ‘good Samaritans’ who challenge and serve humanity “as a criterion for judging every economic, political, social and religious project” (FT 69). FT may seem to be bit ‘worldly’, yet it is Francis’ “*heart’s cry*” *appeal* to all people of good will. It proposes a fraternal society to heal all wounds of alienation. It is a *dream* to build a sense of belonging to a single human family (FT 30). Yet, FT is a *summa* of Pope Francis’s social teaching, systematically put up over the last seven years (Tornielli, 2020). Francis is ushering in a time to heal and unite, through social friendship and fraternity.

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Soroj Mullick SDB, a Salesian priest for 29 years in Kolkata Province, has a Licentiate (Faith Education) and a Doctorate (Christian Education). He has authored number of research papers and articles. Email: sorojmullick@gmail.com

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